

THE NEXUS BETWEEN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTISES

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Abstract: *The study was carried out in Ogbia town in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to examine the nexus between environmental education and effective solid waste management practices. A survey method was adopted, where a questionnaire was administered on 210 randomly selected residents to assess their knowledge, attitude and practice of solid waste management. Data gathered was coded and analyzed using descriptive analysis; tables and simple percentages and Pearson IProduct Moment correlation analysis at 0.05 significance level. The study revealed that solid waste management practices of residents were poor; their throw away attitude, dumping, channels, drainages, canals and open spaces as well as burning of solid waste hold far- reaching environmental and health consequences; hence, antithetical to sustainable development. Also, lack of awareness, inadequate waste collection-facilities and lack of funding of relevant agencies were identified as challenges faced by residents. The study recommended the incorporation of environmental education into the school curriculum and community-based initiatives and programmes amongst others; to improve solid waste management practices in Ogbia Town and environs. Results of this study would provide insight for policy-makers and stakeholder to develop effective environmental education programmes that would promote sustainable waste management practices.*

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1.0 Introduction

In most urban towns in Nigeria, greater percentage of the solid waste generated are indiscriminately dumped on the streets, markets places, homes, roadsides and open or underdeveloped land. These solid wastes find their ways into water bodies and drainages systems to cause serious environmental problems. Lamond, Bhattachary and Block, (2012) noted that the barrage of solid wastes and associated environmental and health challenges has made its management imperative. Solid waste includes such arising from domestic, commercial, industrial, agricultural, mining activities and public services among others (Wapwera, Akintunde and Chiroma, 2022); and eventually posing environmental and health hazards because there are no effective policies put in place to encourage waste minimization, re-use, recycling and reduction (Obi-Anija, 2016).

Different waste management approaches have environmental education adopted by government to ensure effective waste management, but sadly the citizens are far from imbibing such management approaches. Hence, issues of solid waste disposal have continued to be a fundamental societal problem. In Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, the last Saturday of every month is declared as monthly sanitation day which usually start from 7:00am and end at 10:00am. However, despite the environmental sanitation programme and policy adopted by the

government to manage the menace, parts of the metropolis are still littered with household solid waste, due to improper or poor waste disposal habits among resident. Citizens over the years have developed the throw away attitude and they dispose waste indiscriminately, and this is antithetical to environmental sustainability.

Most scholars, notably: Eneji, Akpo and Edung, (2017), saw environmental education as having the remedy for the poor waste management behavior of citizens. Similarly, Mubita, Milupi, Monde and Simooya (2022) stated that since environmental problems are basically attitudinal and behavioral driven, they canonly be solved through mindset, attitude and behavioural changes, which environmental education offers. Likewise, Motunrayo and Kobani (2024) noted that ignorance is one of the major reasons for indiscriminate waste disposal. Also, it was the opinion of the authors that the people are not made aware of the consequences of their indiscriminate waste practices to the environment and their personal health; thereby underscoring the environmental education for Environment education.

It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate the role of environmental education in solid waste management practices in Yenagoa metropolis, with a view to identify the challenges to effective solid waste management requires and proffer strategies to be adopted to address such environmental and health issues related to solid waste management

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in Yenagoa metropolis.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Environmental education on Solid Waste Management

According to John and Fredrick (2021) environmental education for sustainable development remains a valuable subject of contemporary society, which is characterized with environmental issues such as solid waste management, climate change, pollution, loss of biodiversity and resource degradation. They noted that the delivery of environmental education is based on values of knowledge, dispositions, competencies and responsible behaviour towards the environment. They reported that environmental education is a transformative tool to learners since it prepares learners with skills, attitudes, knowledge and values to resolve environmental problems. It promotes environmental activism and action-oriented resolution of environmental issues.

The full benefits of environmental education are challenged by limited human capacity, questionable professionalism, limited resources and poor transformation of knowledge to practice. These challenges however, can be alleviated through community engagement in formulating environmental education programmes, multidisciplinary engagements and research on environmental education (EE) delivery and quality. Environmental education is the lifeline to environmental sustainability.

According to Kobani and Wani (2022), to

overcome the crisis associated with solid waste “consciences of the individuals need to be raised through environmental education, inculcation of sustainable consumption practices on waste management for efficient participation. The individuals and community participation in waste management activities from decision making, and structural reforms among others, will increase their sense of belonging and ownership which can bring about improvements in the environment. Hence, waste managers need to take steps to enhance the public knowledge or education of waste management (McAllister, 2015).

According to Wapwera, Akintunde and Rhila (2022), the lack of education and awareness of effective waste management practices is one of the major issues in developing countries. The authors further stated that in Nigeria, due to a lack of education and awareness in waste management, individuals in various communities turn to blame the government for improper waste management. Akintunde (2017) noted that awareness and knowledge did not necessarily imply pro-environmental action; he explained that when people lack interest in environmental issues, it means that they are uninformed, affecting their actions and make them feel not included in waste management decision-making regimes. In a study carried out in Gabon, Botswana, McAllister (2015) found out that even though citizens were aware of recycling and other sustainable waste

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management techniques, it did not translate into participation in pro- environmental activities. The author noted that a lack of interest in the environment culminated into a culture of non-participation of communities in decision making processes which supported the lack of responsibility for solid waste issues and pollution. The author argued that when citizens are given education about waste management, they turn to be informed, knowing the essence of waste management, become responsible and participate in decision making.

McAllister (2015) said that environmental education plays a crucial role in improving solid waste management by fostering a positive attitude and behaviour changes towards waste by empowering individuals with the knowledge and skills to understand the impact of waste, adopt sustainable practices and participate actively and support such policies on waste management practices.

2.2 Concept of Environmental Education

Environmentalists, notably Hassenforter, Pittock, Barretaau, Daniel and Ferrand (2010), posited that the solution to environmental problems bedeviling our society lies in educating people to become part of the solution of saving the environment. In addition, the authors defined environmental education as a process that enables individuals to explore environment issues, participate in problem-solving and get citizens to improve the

environment. Similarly, Koger (2013) noted that the solutions to the world's environmental problems and challenges, including issues of solid waste hinge more on the modification of people's behaviours and attitudes towards the environment, particularly through psychological and environmental education processes. According to Carter and Simmon (2010), environmental education is the development of environmentally literate citizens in skills, knowledge, attitude and values. However, Motunrayo and Kobani (2024) noted that environmental education is an evolving concept and goes beyond transmission of mere skill, knowledge relating to the environment and involves development of a culture of ideas and behaviours that maintain and sustain environmental quality.

Likewise, Mubita et al, (2022), noted that the World's environmental problems would not be tackled by the same mindset that led to their existence in the first place, as the solutions do not solely lie in technology and its advancement, but in mindset and behavioral changes, and perhaps through the instrumentation of environmental education; as Esteban-Ibanaz, Cid-Lucena, Munoz and Claros, (2020) posited that education is one of the most powerful tools that can be used to modify people's behaviour globally. Furthermore, Carter and Simmon 2010, averred that environmental education enables the citizenry to ask questions about their surrounding and world at large.

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Environmental education enhances the citizenry awareness, grasp of and understanding of environment processes and systems including human behaviour, value systems and attitudes to the environment in totality, identify and formulate potential solutions to the world's environmental challenges and problems (Neaman *et al*, 2018).

According to Choulhary and Tiwary (2019), environmental education is an opportunity to acquire skills, attitude and knowledge that is essential in ecological improvement and further underscored that environmental education is key, which primary aim is to present or disseminate environmental information in order to motivate people into action. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2021) stated that environmental education is important in engendering respect for nature and enhancing public awareness for environment and need for its conservation. Furthermore, the UNESCO, 2021 summarized the main aims of environmental education as follows;

i. To show the economic, social political and ecological interdependence of the modern world, in which decisions and actions by different countries can have international repercussion. Hence, environmental education should help to develop a sense of responsibility and solidarity among countries and regions as the foundation for a new international order to guarantee the improvement of the world.

ii. To succeed in making individuals and communities understand the complex nature of the natural and the built environment. Also, to acquire the knowledge, values, attitude and practical skills to participate responsibly, effectively in solving social problems and in the management of the quality of the environment.

2.3 Concept of Solid Waste and Waste Management

The United State Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2018), defined solid waste as any garbage or refuse, sludge from a waste water treatment plant, water supply treatment plant, or air pollution control quality and other discarded materials, including solid, liquid, semi-solid or contained gaseous material resulting from industrial, commercial, mining and agricultural operations, from community activities. Similarly, Wapwera, Akintunde and Chiroma (2022), described solid wastes materials arising from domestic, commercial, industrials, agricultural, mining activities and public services among others. Solid waste is any moveable solid object that the owner decides to dispose of (Obi-Anija, 2016). Nonetheless, the EPA (2018) defined waste as any material or substance, regardless of form, that is considered unwanted, unusable or worthless after its primary use: it is a broad concept encompassing discarded material, by products and substances that have lost their intended value.

According to USEPA (2018), Key aspects of waste include;

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i. *Unwanted or unusable*: It is something that the owner or producer no longer finds useful or has no further use for.

ii. *Subjectivity*: What constitutes waste can be subjective. That is one person's trash might be another's treasure, highlighting the importance of context.

iii. *Diverse forms*: Waste can be solid, liquid or gaseous, hazardous or non-hazardous organic or inorganic.

iv. *Sources*: Waste is generated from various sources, including industrial, commercial, domestic and agricultural activities. In recent times, the rate and quantity of solid waste generation have increased because most human activities generate waste (Brunner and Rechberger, 2014; Amasuo and Baird, 2016). Vergara and Tchobanoglous (2012), stated that as population and purchasing power of people increases, more goods are produced to meet increasing demand, thereby leading to the production of more waste. These continuous flows of waste resulting from human activities, overburdened the environment (Marche Hini, Ridolsi and Rustici, 2007). Solid wastes are disposed of in dumpsites on designated land either owned by government or private owned; in some cases, in burrow pits and empty spaces unauthorized. Generally, the attitude of citizens on indiscriminate dumping of solid waste in strategic location mounting to heaps of refuse and promoting dirty environment has engendered concern calling for effective

strategies of solid waste management. Beranek (1992) argued that the provision of an efficient solid waste management system has become as important as other essential amenities such as electricity, airports and highways. Hence, Ghani, Lagana, Manni, Musmanno and Vigo (2014) stated that a proper organization of solid waste management has become essential.

The concept of waste management is a complex and multifaceted field that requires careful planning, resources allocation, community awareness, and enforcement of legal frameworks to ensure effective and sustainable waste practices (Kobani, 2014). The author noted that it involves several stages of activities where people's participation harnessed in the collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal of various waste materials, with focus on minimizing waste, recovering resources and reducing the environmental and health impacts of waste, while efficiently maximizing resources. Solid waste management is defined as the discipline associated with control of generation, storage, collection, transport/transfer, processing and disposal of solid waste materials in a way that best addresses the raise of public health conservation, economic, aesthetic engineering and other environmental considerations.

According to the World Bank (2020), the primary goal of solid waste management is reducing and eliminating adverse impacts of waste materials on human health and the

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environment to support economic development and superior quality of life. Furthermore; they highlighted six functional components of waste management system, which include:

i. *Waste Generation:* This encompasses any activities involved in identifying materials that are no longer useable and are either gathered for systematic disposal or throw away, on-site handling, storage or processing. This rotates to activities at the point of waste generation, which facilitates easier collection, for instance, waste bins are placed at sites that generates sufficient waste.

ii. *Waste collection:* This is a crucial phase of waste management; this includes activities such as placing waste collection bins, collection waste from those bins, and accumulating trash in the location where the collection vehicle is emptied.

iii. *Waste transfer/transport:* These are the activities involved in moving waste from the local waste collection locations to the regional waste disposal side in large waste transport vehicles.

iv. *Waste processing/recovery:* This refers to the facilities, equipment, and technique employed to recover reusable or recyclable materials from the waste stream and to improve the effectiveness of other functional elements of waste management and disposal; the final stage of waste management. It involves the activities aimed at the systematic disposal of waste materials in locations such as landfills or waste-

to-energy facilities.

Furthermore, World Bank (2020), noted that based on the foregoing, people participation in waste management is essential in the following areas:

i. Reduce, reuse and recycling (RRR) of waste

ii. Not to throw the waste/litter on the streets drains, open spaces, water bodies among others.

iii. Storage of organic/bio-degradable and recyclable waste separately at source

iv. Primary collection of waste

v. Community storage/collection of waste in flats, multi-stoned buildings, societies, commercial complexes among others.

vi. Manage excrete of pets, dogs, cats approximately

vii. Waste processing/disposal at the community level, and

viii. Pay adequately for the services provided.

Vergara and Tchobanogious (2012), noted that all of these aforementioned processes require adequate environmental education for effective participation. Also, they also posited that to enhance waste management practices, government should adopt community-based approach, where the people are part of the project: they should be able to see it as their responsibility and contributions to improve their quality of life.

3.0 The Study Area

The study was conducted in Ogbia Local

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Government Area of Bayelsa State. The local government has a total area of 1698 square kilometers. It is important to note that Ogbia LGA has an historic significance as the site where crude oil was first discovered in commercial quantity in Nigeria, specifically in Oloibiri village (Abowei, 1996). The study area is nets in natural resources which include oil/gas with oil wells in most communities and projects crisis-crossing the area. The geographical coordinate of the central point of the study area which is Ogbia town is found within latitude 4°46'60¹¹ north and longitude 6°19'60¹¹ East. The area lies in the west equatorial climatic region of the Niger Delta,

and typically a humid tropical climate characterized by lying rainfall and high temperature (Gobo, 1998). The temperature of the area is 25.5°c with little seasonal variations. The vegetation cover of the study area is typical of the fresh water areas characterized by grasses and trees, and surface soil showing moderate suitability for crop.

The major economic activities are agriculture, which include fishing, farming, forestry/lumbering, gathering of wild forest products and tapping of palm wine and brewing of local gin are the primary economic activities in the areas. Allison – Oguru, Zuofa and Berepubo (1999).

Fig 3.1: Map Showing the Study Area

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4.0 Methodology

The study design is the survey design. The research methodology used both primary and secondary data. The research used mainly questionnaire survey which involved the utilization of a structured questionnaire to illicit relevant data and direct physical observation. Oral interview was conducted. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used. The total population of 686 forms the target population. A total of 322 of the questionnaire were distributed to Ogbia town in Ogbia Local Government Area. A sample size of 322 was determined using TaroYamane formula for determination of sample size (Kplovie, 2011).

Table 1: Environmental education/Training Received

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	31	14.7
No	160	76.2
	19	9.0
Total	210	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

The table showed that only 31 respondents representing 15% of respondent had received a form of environmental education, while 160 respondents (76%) said they have not received any form of environmental education. Also, the table showed that 9% of respondents declined providing any answer to the question. The result underscored the need for more environmental education programme to improve knowledge

$$\frac{n}{1 + N(e)^2} = N \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The sample size of the area is 322. Of this number, 210 copies of questionnaire were retrieved from respondents, male and female households head and professionals in the built environment. Descriptive statistics was the method used to analyze data collected for the study.

5.0 Analysis of Data and Discussions

This section presents the findings of the study on the role of environmental education in effective solid waste management practice. The data is presented in tables, figures and graphs, followed by interpretation and discussion of the findings.

and awareness of solid waste management practice in the study area. As noted by Esteba-Ibanez et al, (2020) environmental education is one of the most powerful tools that can be used to modify people’s behaviours and concern as well as value for environmental management practices; and improved participation in environmental decision-making processes (Wapwera et al, 2022).

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Table 2: Major Method of Solid Wastes Disposal

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Municipal waste collection	57	27.1
Opening dumping	113	53.8
Burying	2	0.9
Burning	38	18.1
Total	210	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2 illustrated that 27% of respondents disposed of solid (household) waste through municipal waste collection, 54% through opening dumping on designated dumpsites roadsides and even in drainages and waterways. The table also showed that 18% of respondents dispose of household wastes through burning, while only 2 respondents representing about 0.9% said they bury their household wastes.

On whether or not they separate recyclable for non-recyclable materials before disposal, 189 respondents representing 90% of total number

of respondents said they do not separate recyclable for non-recyclable materials before disposal, while only 10% of respondents said they do separations before disposal of solid wastes. Obviously, waste segregation and recycling practices are low among respondents; hence, suggesting the need for programmes that promote effective solid waste management practices. Likewise, the fact that greater number of respondents still indulge in open dumping underscored the need for environmental education. Indiscriminate open dumping into a canal is illustrated in Figure 4.1

Figure 4.1: Open Dumping in a Canal

Table 3: Participation in Neighbourhood Waste Management Practices.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	18.5
No	150	71.4
Abstinance	21	10.0
Total	210	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

According to results 150 respondents accounting for 71% of respondents did not participate in neighbourhood waste management practises, while only 39 respondents accounting for about 19% affirmed their participation. However, 21 (10%) of respondents declined any response to the item on the questionnaire. Research finding showed that participation in solid waste management practice is low, despite

the importance of participation in the attainment of sustainable development. While emphasizing the role of citizen participation in solid waste management practices, Squire (2006) noted that environmental issues, including issues of solid waste management are best handled with the participation of all citizens at a relevant level. Furthermore, he stated that the rational of effective citizen participation is clearly based on the fact that

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every individual generate waste and can be properly disposed or managed. affected directly or indirectly if such waste is not

Table 4: Major Challenges Faced in Effective Solid Waste Management Practice

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of public awareness/ education	59	28.1
Inadequate waste collection / disposal systems	29	13.8
Inadequate regulatory framework	32	15.2
Insufficient funding/ financial resources	39	18.7
Lack of community participation	51	24.2
Others		
Total	210	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Analysis of data on major challenges faced in practicing effective solid waste management showed that 28% of respondents identified lack of public awareness/ education, 14% of respondents identified inadequate waste collection and disposal system, 15% of respondents identified inadequate regulatory framework. Also, the table showed that 19% identified insufficient funding/financial resources of solid waste management programmes as a major challenge, while 51% respondents accounting for 24% identified lack

of community participation as a major challenge to practicing effective solid waste management.

It is important to note that these challenges underscore the need for a comprehensive and integrated approach to solid waste management regime in Yenagoa metropolis. According to Abang (2016), these challenges have necessitated the need for an effective development of solid waste management plans for cities, especially in developing countries as ours, Nigeria can call for greater commitment on the part of environmental policy-makers.

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Table 5: Environmental Education to be Accorded Adequate Attention

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	182	86.6
Disagreed	7	3.3
None	21	10.0
Total	210	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Results of data analysis on whether or not environmental education should be given adequate attention, included in the school curriculum showed that 87.7% of respondents agreed to the affirmative, while 3% of respondents disagreed while, 10% of respondents declined responding to the question. The role of environmental education in solving environmental problems cannot be overstated as posited by Mubita et al (2022); they noted that environmental problems are basically instigated by humans, and are attitudinal and behaviour motivated, so cannot be solved by the same mindset, attitude and behaviour that led to their existence in the first place; but in mindset, attitude and behavior changes, which according to the authors are better and easily achievable through adequate environmental education.

Conclusion

This study investigated the role of environmental education (EE) in enhancing effective solid waste management in Ogbia Town, Bayelsa state. The findings of this study revealed that environmental education plays a

significant role in promoting effective solid waste management practices in Ogbia Town, Yenagoa Metropolis of Bayelsa State. The result of this study aligns with the views of Wapwera et al (2022) who underscored the need for adequate environmental education in pursuing effective waste management practices in urban centre especially in developing countries like Nigeria. In efforts aimed to create environmental awareness, promoting sustainable practices and supporting sustainable development, environmental education can help address the daring issues of solid waste management as well as the identified challenges such as lack of awareness/ education, lack of funding, lack of community participation among others. There is no gain saying that collaborative efforts of government, educators and communities can enhance and promote waste management practices and environmental sustainability.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings, the study recommends as follows:

- i. Environmental education programmes should be introduced in schools' curriculum

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ii. It should be implemented to improve knowledge and awareness of solid waste management practices among residents.

iii. Government should formulate policies and programmes that promote waste segregation and recycling to achieve reduction in the amount of waste and waste sent to landfills and reduce the environmental and health impacts of solid waste.

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iv. To enhance waste management practices, government should adopt community-based approach, where the people are part of the project. They should be able see it as their responsibility and contribution to improve their quality of life.

v. Proper planning and control is required in order to prevent the negative impact of waste on the environment.

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